

Maintaining the Dymaxion House in Henry Ford Museum.

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This paper tells of R. Buckminster Fuller's "Dwelling Machine," the Dymaxion House, and recounts the original project to conserve and reconstruct its prototype as a permanent exhibit in The Henry Ford Museum. Long-term exhibition entails yearly maintenance and eventually required modifications to accommodate visitor traffic. Damages found in 2012 necessitated serious intervention and inspired a testing regime to model the expected longevity of the repaired structure.

In the huge 32,374.8 m² (8-acre) museum that Henry Ford built in the Detroit suburb of Dearborn, an unusual shiny structure will attract you. It is R. Buckminster Fuller's Dymaxion House or "Dwelling Machine": A domed, cage-hung cylinder supported off the ground on a central pole, with wrap-around windows, walls that lower for airflow and a rotating ventilator on top. You can walk inside this 11m (36-foot) diameter "corner-less cottage" and see for yourself how Fuller realized his prototype concept for the "house of the future" circa 1945.

The idea for the dwelling machine had occurred to him more than 20 years earlier. Buckminster Fuller noodled for years with ideas to help humanity by making cheap housing for all by doing "more with

less” – that is more dwelling space using less raw material. The houses would be mass-produced in factories, like cars and airplanes - the 20th century way. The house would require the least possible foundation footprint, and it would be so lightweight that it could be supported on a mast. It would have a myriad of laborsaving devices, with ultimate light and ventilation.

The structural principle would be tension. Fuller’s inspirations were cabled suspension bridges, the rigged mast of sailboats and the ultimate tension structure, the airship (Zeppelin). Like an airship, which is a series of extruded and stamped rings cross-braced with cables and turnbuckles, held together by tension, the Dymaxion House would use aluminum structurally.

Fuller drew numerous iterations of the building that would enclose maximum living space using minimum amount of material. Inspired by the great airship programs of the 1920s, he thought that perhaps a Zeppelin could drop a bomb to make a crater for the foundation and then set down a whole Dymaxion tower. Since it would be on a mast, the family of the future could park its airplane underneath the raised “deck” of their house.

Wherever he could, he promoted his notions about how his new way of mass-producing houses would benefit society. A public relations man suggested he coin the brand “DYNAMAXION” from “dynamic,” “maximum” and “tension,” words that popped up frequently in his lectures. He spoke often “on the philosophy, economics, dynamics, etc., of Dymaxion Design.” However, he was waiting for the right circumstances and the right lightweight, high strength materials to become available cheaply.

In the meantime, he managed to produce a stamped-metal all-in-one “Dymaxion bathroom”, prototype a three-wheeled automobile and designed the “Dymaxion Deployment Unit”, an army barracks made out of corrugated steel Butler grain bins.

Finally, in 1945, when the country was anticipating a post-war housing shortage, he got the backing he needed to form a company, The Dymaxion Dwelling Machine Company, R. Buckminster Fuller Chief Engineer (later simply “Fuller Houses”). Located in the middle of the country in Wichita, KS, the Beech Aircraft Company was ready to re-tool and poised to use the know-how of skilled trades employed until very recently making aluminum planes for the war effort. Fuller set about with a young engineering staff producing hundreds of design drawings and patented the ideas.

His basic design called for a central steel-tube “mast” supported in a relatively small concrete foundation pad. The aluminum sheet-metal “skin” would be supported by the structural “cage” consisting of rings (called “A, B, C and D”, from the top down), cross-braced with turn-buckled cables and rods. The Plexiglas[™] windows would be fixed, but the long sheet-metal walls below them could be lowered for screened air circulation around the entire perimeter. A rotating, louvered ventilator on top could swivel to catch the wind and thus increase air-movement draught inside the house. The rather complicated “deck” structure theoretically hangs by the cage on the mast. The deck has 96 break-formed tapered, “U”-shaped aluminum sheet-metal beams arrayed in a circle between the “Inner Z ring” and the “Outer Z ring,” with a cabled truss between every other beam supporting a medial “L” bracket. The tapered, bevel-edged plywood floorboards clip to the beams with long strips of formed-sheet aluminum. The deck is secured to the ground around the outer edge with turnbuckle “tie-downs.” Fuller wanted the house to be shipped in aluminum cans and be assembled in three days.

His design team worked with skilled trades from the Beech Aircraft Company to produce two prototypes and try out various design concepts. They produced copious design drawings, trying ideas like Plexiglas[™] for the ventilator and a rubberized fabric ceiling. An indoor (“Danbury”) prototype was built for promotional purposes. A second outdoor (“Barwise”) prototype was used for unsophisticated engineering tests. They reportedly piled bricks up on one side to see what would happen. But issues like

fatigue of these aircraft alloys were not well understood at the time. The company finally failed because too many of Fuller's cherished ideas were proving difficult to realize.

One of the financial backers bought all the prototype parts and built a two-story version of the house for himself on a lake outside Wichita. The Graham family was not satisfied with life in a "Dwelling Machine." They sealed off the ventilator, built the deck on a concrete block foundation with a spiral staircase up the middle, and added more conventional masonry structures to it. They painted it and coated the inside with tarry insulation material. They abandoned the house in the early 1970s.

The Henry Ford museum acquired the house and all the parts in 1991 and sent a group of staff and volunteers to disassemble it. Damages were extensive and included lots of rot to outer edges of the wooden floorboards and the aluminum support beams due to leaky or missing windows. Hygroscopic insulation made things worse in the floor beams. Elements of the cage were bent inadvertently during disassembly. The disassembly team reported seeing bending they called "potato chipping" of the B and C rings once cables were released.

A few years after the recovery from its Wichita site, the museum formed a new conservation team to restore and re-erect the house inside Henry Ford Museum. The exhibition team decided early on that public access was paramount. The design of the protracted restoration program commenced with a Historic Structures Report on the history and significance of the artifact. Early on it was determined that the "point in time" the house would be restored to should reflect the "finished" prototype (an oxymoron?) but that the functions and structural uniqueness of the "dwelling machine" needed to be revealed as well.

James Ashby, a conservation-trained architect coordinated the three-year effort. The project conservator from the museum's permanent staff was Clara Deck. Tim Brewer, a multi-skilled work foreman, came on as a volunteer and then was hired full time; he worked with up to six part-time technicians dedicated to the project. The conservation team confronted an assemblage of over thirty-six hundred parts, some of which had been used in one of the prototypes, as well as many "extra" parts. The team set about system-by-system, checking how many parts were extant and their condition.

Damages included modifications and coatings but most of the worst problems were due to water ingress and inappropriate assembly of metals with masonry. A significant number of the "deck" parts suffered from spectacular corrosion with lamellar exfoliation, especially on the extruded parts. There was also a significant amount of galvanic action from ferrous fasteners and where parts were made of sandwiched steel beside aluminum. (These elements were to be made of aluminum in the final design, but the Fuller team had made steel/aluminum parts in the prototype to save cost). Karen Trentleman, then scientist at the Detroit Institute of Arts, helped identify the alloys and characterize the corrosion. Some of the original 1945 parts still retained their manufacturing roll-marking stamps. Almost all of the aluminum was 2000-series alloys, using current nomenclature, which is an aircraft alloy containing about 4% copper. These wrought alloys are ductile and formable, but their 4% copper content makes them corrosion-prone. Corrosion susceptibility increases dramatically in the vicinity of corrosive sources like mortar and concrete blocks. Typical corrosion products found were aluminum hydroxides that formed crusts and caused a fair amount of pitting as well as filiform corrosion. Trentleman worked with other metallurgists at Ford and General Motors who confirmed the composition of various parts. These scientists got very excited about how the Alclad (pure aluminum metalurgically bonded on 2000-series alloy sheet) roof panels had aged and altered over those years in the hot Wichita sun. They wrote a paper about it for a scientific journal.

The museum also hired a structural engineer, Tom Fitzpatrick, who was required to legally sign off on the structure for public occupancy. He hired his own metallurgist, Donna Walker to advise him about the structural properties of the aluminum. She performed conductivity tests to determine corrosion susceptibility of component parts. Fitzpatrick did finite element analysis on structural parts. Finite element analysis is used to calculate component displacements, strains, and stresses under internal and external loads. He analyzed the loads on the beams, modeling where the deflection, bending and shear force would occur. He used a “forty pounds per square foot” (195 kg/m²) rule, which is a U.S. standard for a residential structure load, not a public structure load. He recommended stiffening the floor structure with a steel “I” -beam bracket cantilevered off the foundation at the mast that could shore up the inner Z-ring. Whereas this support structure circumvents the original Fuller deck design, it was not seen as unduly invasive because it supports, but is not fastened to, any original component.

The conservation work on component parts started with cleaning and stripping off paint. Removal of the tarry waterproofing substance required the whole team to get specialized hazardous material handling training, because it was full of asbestos.

There was extensive testing for corrosion removal techniques. The team tried but rejected caustic proprietary gels because they were hard to clear from huge and complicated shapes with crevices. After testing with specialists from the 3M Company, and representatives at Dynabrade, the method finally determined used a variety of fine rotating bristle discs. The testing criteria were based on finish quality, and what kind of stresses the abrasive technique would impart to the metal surface. The goal was to remove as little metal as possible.

Parts that would not be seen, such as the floor beams, were particle-blasted with aluminum oxide at very low pressure. But as the beams were blasted the team found hairline cracks that had been hidden under the corrosion crusts. The cracks seemed to re-occur in the same position: always on edges near the

middle of the beam. These beams were rejected and another one taken from the pile of parts. In the final assembly, one third of the ninety-six beams were made of new break-formed metal after the cracking problem was found. The aluminum used for the replacements was a close match to the original alloy and thickness.

The long-term performance of the beams was of concern to the metallurgist. She recommended solution heat-treating some parts. Heat treating is a well-established procedure whereby manufactured parts are heated to a temperature close to their melting point and, with a very slow cooling, returned to a specific temper. The temper designation is alloy-specific and improves the corrosion resistance and also the elongation and toughness and corrosion-resistance of parts. This procedure was recommended for the rings and beams of the deck structure. It was difficult to find a local company who could handle the 4.1 meter (13. 6-foot) beams. Heat-treating is indeed non-reversible, but was considered essential. There are plenty of unused, never treated parts from 1945 still retained in the warehouse of The Henry Ford should further metallurgical research on the old aluminum be warranted.

The outer skin panels were polished using aircraft abrasive polishes, with large variable speed rotating polishers with soft pads. This was a long and multi-stage process. A few skilled guys with good ventilation and personal protective equipment carefully degreased the aluminum parts to prepare them for the critical spray-applied coating. The coating chosen to keep the shiny skin parts shiny was cellulose nitrate Agatenetm due to superior adhesion and ease of application to large panels. The under-floor parts received a coating of Incralactm. Incralac is a solvent-born thermoplastic acrylic that was designed to protect copper and therefore thought to be advantageous for our 2000-series sheet aluminum, but it had poor adhesion on the shiny skin panels.

Badly damaged components were made of new metal, using modern alloys very similar to the originals. Some parts received riveted patches. Visitors can detect which of the roof panel “gores” are original; they are the ones with the patches along the bottom.

Working on this project in the Detroit area was a great benefit because the team could employ local manufacturers and prototyping shops familiar with metalworking and eager to commit to interesting jobs. Ashby found shops large enough to laser-cut shiny 12-foot long (3.7 m) roof panels and break-form the 13.6-foot long (4.1m) replacement deck beams. Brewer knew of a prototype shop willing to tackle the re-construction of Fuller’s cherished “ovolving shelves” – the motor-driven aluminum boxes on a track that rotated while keeping the boxes always upright. Future Tool re-engineered the “ovolving” tracks to use wheels made of Delrin[™] (an engineered low-friction thermoplastic) for longwearing performance. The ovolving shelves have functioned continuously since then.

The floorboards were an interesting challenge as well. About one-third of the house could re-use existing plywood boards, with minor repairs for delamination and some re-finishing. The team was pleased to find out that the same manufacturer that had provided lumber to the original Fuller project were still in business and producing fir ply with the same number of plies (5). Brewer created a jig to make new bevel-edged wedge-shaped floorboards. The factor the team did not anticipate was the difference in “figure”; old-growth fir is typically close-grained whereas the newly harvested quicker-growing wood has a broad figure. This required the team to apply traditional faux-finish “graining” techniques to the new boards so they would integrate better with the originals.

The floorboards clip to the deck beams with long die-formed strips of sheet aluminum. These smallest of parts proved a trial to reproduce. The team found that few technicians had the know-how of mid-century aircraft-builders. The shape was so complicated to bend that the material cracked while being

formed. The museum's then Curator of Industry had a friend, a retired technician from General Motors, who produced the clips in a multi-phase production in his backyard shop using steel and wood dies to slowly form the metal clips.

In some cases, older technologies were employed to repair or make parts for the "house of the future." New doorsills were machined out of thick aluminum bar-stock using planers and shapers in the museum's own "Armington and Sims" machine shop, a working turn-of-the-20th-century shop in Greenfield Village (a part of The Henry Ford campus). The beautiful compound-curved "cowling" panels on the outer edge of the deck required re-fabrication because the team had only a few damaged examples of the originals. Had the house gone into production, this element would have been mass-produced using a huge metal stamping press like a car bumper. The reproductions were fabricated using an English wheeling machine – another late 19th century sheet-metal-working tool.

Fig 1. The Dymaxion House inside Henry Ford Museum. Drawing by A. Titenkoff from The Collections of The Henry Ford.

Finally, team members started to assemble the house inside Henry Ford Museum. A grant from the U.S. Federal Institute for Museum & Library Services helped fund a public program on the conservation process for the public during the long assembly phase. (The online “Conservator’s Journal” is still accessible on the THF website.) Each piece was clipped, bolted, cabled and, riveted into place. The team used dozens of different kinds of fasteners. Many were aluminum rivets. Bolts were stainless steel and these were always separated from the aluminum parts with Delrin™ washers to avoid future galvanic action. Stainless steel turnbuckles were sourced from local sailboat shops.

A year after the house opened to the public, the museum engaged the services of a talented intern preservation architect through the US-International Council for Museums and Sites (ICOMOS) program. With advice from the Historic American Buildings Survey/Historic American Engineering Record (HABS/HAER) program of the U.S. Library of Congress, Alex Titenkoff produced a series of beautiful measured drawings of the Dymaxion House “as built” in Henry Ford Museum.

The Dymaxion House represents a rather unusual case of the merging of architectural conservation, which generally gives priority to preserving aesthetic and structural integrity, with museum conservation, which generally gives priority to preserving the material authenticity of an object (along with the artist’s original intent). This blending of conservation philosophies and standards in the reconstruction of the Dymaxion House is perhaps best reflected in the decision to exhibit the house inside the museum. While the house was designed to be an outdoor structure, and therefore may have been more appropriately placed in an outdoor setting within the collection of Greenfield Village, its origins inside an aircraft factory provided a precedent for indoor installation. Based on the fragility of the building as a prototype, its placement inside the climate-controlled environment of the Henry Ford

Museum will undoubtedly prove to be the most significant treatment decision with regards to its long-term preservation.

From the start, the exhibit was planned so that the public could walk through the house. An exhibit meant to re-create the feel of Fuller's Beech Aircraft warehouse shop introduces guests to the "back story" of the development of the house. A ramp takes you up to deck level. The idea was to present the house like a salesman's sample, at the time when the Beech aircraft workers' wives got to tour the house in 1946. Guests walk in the front door, through three rooms separated by closet pods and out the back door. The first bedroom shows some interesting features like the corner-less bathroom, revolving closets and the "ovolving" shelves. The second bedroom has layers stripped away to show the structure and how the wall panels lower for screened ventilation. This "cut-away" room also exposes the "mast", the rotating ventilator and the water-collecting interior "carlins" (or gutters) that support the roof "gores". The living room is cordoned off from visitors, but is furnished to look just like the 1946 spread when the house was featured in Fortune Magazine.

At first guests were guided through the house by museum presenters pretending to "sell" the house, wearing frumpy 1940s clothing. This helped limit the number of visitors allowed in the structure at one time, which the engineer had set at approximately fifteen. The space is so limited that any more than that would feel quite crowded. The guided tour notion was discarded after about six years when museum management instituted a "self-guided" approach and dropped the "1st person" circa 1946 presentation. This change meant installation of additional, possibly intrusive and confusing, Plexiglas barriers to keep fragile areas off-limits. One of the changes was to remove the original bathroom door and replace it with a full-length Plexiglas barrier; some folks still ask if they had see-through doors in the mid-1940s. Another change was to fix the pulley-activated "moveable wall" in the cut-away room to make it tamper-proof, which unfortunately makes understanding the "drop-down walls" more difficult.

Additional signage in the “cut-away” room does not adequately explain the complicated features like the rotating ventilator, air circulation through floor beams and water-collecting neoprene gutters. Many visitors do not “get” the intricate structural tension concept. A yearly shut-down allows the current conservation team to make slight improvements to visitor-caused wear. Upgrades to the entire exhibition in the near future may improve didactic material with more drawings. Perhaps cartoons could explain, for instance, how rainwater might come inside the “carlin” gutters that support the roof “gores” and be collected by the internal neoprene trough and carried to an under-house cistern.

After more than ten years of continuous exhibition and about three hundred thousand pairs of feet per year, the museum’s inspection routine involves squeezing under the house with less than 45.7cm (18 inches) of space to look for problems. It is a confined space and hard to photograph. Every year the cables are measured and re-tensioned as necessary to maintain the structural integrity of the “cage”. Early on, the team’s conservator was obsessed with whether the lacquer would hold up to visitor handling and with looking for what might be new outbreaks of corrosion.

A more serious observation was evidence that the cage might be racking. This was seen in roof gores that no longer line up and seem to be deforming. The conservation team wanted to measure how the cage might be deflecting. What was out of alignment? How level is each ring compared to each other in this tension structure? So team members regularly climb up into the ventilator and look at the “A” ring. They have developed a technique to rig up a three hundred and sixty degree laser level on the mast and position a measuring rule to record the alignment of the rings. Conservators have been able to compare three years of data, and found that the A and C rings are slightly out-of true relative to each other, although they have not changed position. Doubtless, the conservation team could employ a more sophisticated 3D laser-scanning measuring technique for increased accuracy as a comparison technique, but this low-tech method has worked.

A more troubling discovery during routine inspection was the crushing that could be felt in the floor, especially in areas where crowds lingered for the presentation. Lifting up the carpet, it was evident that boards had shifted. What was happening to the floor structure underneath, especially near the middle of the beams in the area of an “L” bracket and truss? No problems were found on a not-too-thorough look in 2009. But in 2012 the team found extensive cracking on the under-floor beams.

The cracking and failure was found on the new (2001-era) beams as well as the old, always in the same pattern: extending from the edge of the “L” bracket that was supporting the kingpost of the truss under every-other beam. The cracking typically extended about 5cm (2 inches) from the upper edges of the “L” bracket and travelled out along the break-formed ninety-degree corner of the beam. The crack propagation on the worst areas eventually lead to the formation of lozenge-shaped pieces that would in due time crack all the way and fall out. It was clear that the metal was failing due to repeated-cycling fatigue. The root cause of the fatigue failure was the stress concentration resulting from the sharp corner of the “L” bracket.

Conservators started to map the location and extent of the cracking. They found that the pattern of damage corresponded exactly to the pattern of traffic from three hundred thousand pairs of feet per year.

A repair program was quickly developed. Back in 2001, team members had said they pitied the fools who would have to take the structure back apart; not suspecting it would be they. Once a few boards were off the floor, conservators could really see the extent of the problem: major structural cracking and metal loss. Getting at the problem meant major disassembly of the deck. So they disconnected the closet pods and shoved them aside, which allowed them to open up the sills and bang out the floorboards along aluminum-clip channels. Opening up half of the floor at a time exposed the cracked aluminum beams.

To arrest the cracks from propagating further, the ends of each tiny crack was drilled with a sixteenth of an inch (1.5mm) hole. Working above the floor required the fabrication of a temporary plywood bridge in order to lean over and drill out the ends of the cracks. Each crack-end hole had its edge beveled, top and bottom, which is standard aircraft repair practice. Beveling blunts the existing cracks and reduces the stress concentration in the metal.

By the time all the cracking had been found, the team realized it was even more extensive than they first thought: more than half of the 96 beams were affected, even in the third of the house where the public could not walk. Richard Jeryan, a volunteer mechanical engineer who still had many contacts at Ford Motor Company and knew of the best local firms who specialize in aluminum part prototyping, suggested the team hire Metro Tech, a local company who could do the job quickly. They made patches of aluminum twice as thick as the original beam that would be riveted in place under the deck and secured with a 3M adhesive recommended by an engineer at Ford Motor Company.

Patching the beams required the central portions be shored up during work because of course the “L” bracket and truss underneath the beams had to be removed. The sharp edge on the “L” bracket was carefully machined to a rounded-off profile.

In addition to the repair, it was decided to spread the visitor load further by installing 9.5mm (3/8 inch) plywood over the artifact-floor where the public walks. This was perhaps the conservators’ most brutal intervention to the artifact, because it required screwing directly into the existing plywood floor (hidden under carpeting).

After all this work, how would the team know whether the repair was enough? It was about this time that Jeryan, Brewer and Deck went out to the museum’s storage area to look at the old reject beams and

found lots of evidence of exactly the same problem. They recalled the initial concern for the future performance of the beams by Fitzpatrick, the structural engineer and Walker, his contract metallurgist.

The cracking of the Dymaxion House floor beams is due to high-cycle metal fatigue, which is a phenomenon that causes materials to fracture after a period of cyclic loading (like bending.) The fatigue cracks in the beams developed as a result of how the floor system was designed. It turns out that a very long, tapered “U”-shaped sheet-metal trough, even one supported with a cabled truss underneath, does not work. The 1945 design did not adequately accommodate the cyclic loading. The discovery of the cracked beams never used in museum storage confirmed that even of the residential use in the Graham version of the house had caused the characteristic cracking.

Deck, the project conservator, was worried about whether corrosion might have been involved in the fatigue cracking. New metallographic analysis of the cracked-out fragments at Ford Motor Company confirmed the alloy composition and described the crack propagation mechanism, which reassured her that corrosion wasn't a cause.

With input from engineers at Ford Motor Company across the street from the museum, the museum's resident volunteer engineer set about designing a testing program using strain gaging. Strain gauging is a well-established procedure familiar to civil and mechanical engineers to determine the principle stresses and characterize fatigue loading on a structure. Residual stress gauges measure stress in the floor structure under empty dead load. The linear gauges measure the stress under live loads. The stress and strain measurements are gathered with proprietary software. The crack gauges first detect a new crack and then monitor how fast it is advancing.

Gauges were placed in high traffic areas and also in the living room that gets less foot traffic, but has no covering over the floor to spread loads. Installing the gauges was very finicky work and was carried out

by highly experienced technicians from Ford Motor Company. Working in 45.7cm (18 inches) of space, soldering tiny contacts above one's head is a challenge. Each gauge was wired and connected to the data logging system, which were positioned at the mast opening.

The crack gauges detect a new crack when an electrical contact is broken, and the propagation gauge beyond that can inform how fast a crack is moving (propagating). The monitoring station requires an operator to check monthly. If the light goes on at every location, there is no crack.

The engineers positioned the five testing strain gauges on the underside of four different beams in strategic location. The gauges were adhered on the beam right next to the patch, arrayed in locations that would give the engineers meaningful data. The residual stress was tested when the house was empty and the live load data was collected over a busy 4th of July weekend. For the residual load, the rosettes with three gauges arranged in a circle measures the residual stress in a material as that stress is relieved when the center is drilled according to an ASTM standard. Data has to be collected during drilling when nobody is in the house. Workers had a hard time meeting the standard in the confined space and had to rig up a drill and borrow a pair of young, 20-year old eyes to see precisely where the hole had to go. The data collection system was wired up along the beams to the data acquisition center where Karnafel collected it from Ford Motor with proprietary software.

Jeryan performed the calculations based on Miner's rule using the live and residual load data. The rule states that the total fatigue damage is the sum of the damage increment done by each strain reversal cycle. Total fatigue life is the inverse of total damage. Each cycle generates a small amount of damage that accumulates over time. The fatigue analysis programs run for the team at Ford estimated the total damage and the time it would take for the new cracks to begin again. These calculations were made to

estimate the fatigue life of the floor structure, taking into account the properties of the materials and using well-established methodology and analysis modules developed at the Ford Motor Company.

Jeryan was confident in his determination that ongoing cracking will not be a concern for about 140 years. The analysis provided by this testing regime gives the museum confidence that the Dymaxion House will remain a much-loved attraction in the Henry Ford Museum for many years to come. The efforts to conserve, restore and maintain this house continue to reveal insights into Fuller's prototyping process that can be used to inform the public as well as scholars. Conservators remain vigilant as they work to preserve the significance of this unique structure.

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Both my colleague James Ashby and I have brought aspects of the Dymaxion House project to conferences throughout the world. Most recently at the ICOM Metals Committee for Conservation's Aluminum conference in Washington in April 2014.

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This paper is dedicated to Richard Jeryan, who passed away this year.

Clara Deck is Senior Conservator at The Henry Ford. She has designed and supervised conservation treatments for thousands of objects from a carousel, steam engines and automobiles to furniture, decorative arts and toys. She has work on dozens of exhibitions, numerous loans and ongoing storage upgrades. A member of the American Institute for Conservation, she has served as a grant reviewer for IMLS, NEH and Save America's Treasures. She has a particular interest in industrial artifacts, modern materials and mechanical musical contraptions.

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